

TOURIST RESOURCES OF GEORGIA AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS**Gelashvili M.***Samtskhe-Javakheti State University**Faculty of Business Administration Associate Professor**Orcid 0000-0002-4153-8451*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20449081>**Abstract**

The development of the tourism sector in Georgia, along with agritourism, is one of the important areas of growth of the national economy. Accordingly, tourism is a leading industry both in our region and around the world, which consistently creates jobs every year. In addition, along with the development of the tourism business, the number of people interested in this area is growing. Georgia, due to the diversity of its natural and climatic conditions, provides good opportunities for the development and implementation of tourism. For example: ecotourism, adventure tourism, agritourism, youth tourism, social tourism, camping and tent tourism. Its development depends on sound strategic management and approach, since it provides the population with additional foreign exchange income, creates a highly efficient, sustainable and environmentally responsible model that has a positive impact on both the environment and the economy and society. However, due to the specifics of tourism, the management of tourism activities in the region requires an integrated approach, in particular, it is necessary to take into account the interests of the local population, since the development of this sector may not bring benefits, but, on the contrary, impede the development of the tourism business.

Based on the above, Georgia has the resources to develop tourism with high potential, but still needs to improve and implement a number of measures. In particular:

- Improve service quality:
 - ✓ Training and retraining of professional personnel
 - ✓ Simplifying international travel
- Infrastructure improvements:
 - ✓ Improved access roads to tourist sites and installation of information boards and signage to facilitate the movement of travellers
 - ✓ Creation of new botanical gardens
 - ✓ Restoration, preservation and use of cultural heritage monuments through the provision of tourist services
 - ✓ Accessibility of tourist facilities for people with disabilities;
- Proper organization of the tourist environment:
 - ✓ Improve information and marketing capabilities
 - ✓ Raising awareness of the tourism potential of the country
 - ✓ Consumer protection.

Although the development of the tourism sector in Georgia requires the renewal of some conditions, the country remains attractive to travelers and is likely to show stable growth in the coming years.

Keywords: tourist resources, stable growth, resource potential, opportunities for recreation, visitor, landscape

The tourism sector occupies a special place in the development of the world economy. Georgia is no exception, since it is a country distinguished by its resource potential, natural, geographical, climatic, recreational opportunities, as well as historical and cultural heritage. In particular, mountain regions and landscapes contribute to the popularization of Georgian traditions and historical and cultural values with their cultural heritage. During the Soviet period, up to four million tourists visited Georgia, the main reason for their arrival was mineral waters and treatment. It is difficult to find a country in the world that would have: a marine climate, up to 2,400 mineral springs, healing mud and caves. Tourists coming to the country had the opportunity not only to recover from various diseases, but also to see the beautiful nature of Georgia with its landscapes and historical monuments. At the current stage, the difficult socio-economic situation has practically closed most of the sanatoriums. Based on the above, medical tourism has significantly lost its function in form and content and has been replaced by sea or mountain resorts.

It is also worth noting that Georgia first presented itself at the World Tourism Exchange in London in 2004, and this practice continues and is becoming more widespread. However, this requires improving the relevant legislative framework and existing laws "On Tourism and Resorts," "On Sanitary Protection Zones of Resorts," "On Regulating the Registration of Tourists Entering and Leaving Georgia," in accordance with international standards. This legislative framework is based on the generally recognized principles of sustainable tourism development, which give priority to stimulating market demand.

Currently, tourism in the region is one of the most promising areas of economic restructuring. Its main advantage is its geographical proximity to the main tourist market - Europe. The appeal of tourism is that it offers something for everyone. Someone likes exotic places, someone - new cities, someone - beach holidays, someone - sightseeing, someone - ecotourism, etc. At this stage, there are 14 state reserves, 13 national parks, 26 protected areas, 40 natural monuments and 5 protected landscapes in Georgia, which significantly increases

the tourist flow. Accordingly, the development of tourism is one of the most powerful drivers of the region, with sufficiently high resources, and over the next decade will be an ever-growing sector.

In Georgia, over the past two years, there has been a downward trend in the number of foreign tourists and visitors entering the country. The number of visits from EU countries has decreased. In particular, in 2025, 34,823 people from the European Union and Great Britain visited Georgia, which is 0.3% less than in 2024. In addition, Germany leads with 62,804 visitors and an annual increase of 15.6%. This year alone, compared to last year (over the same period), their number has increased by almost 3%. While Austria is a country almost the same size as Georgia, and its tourism income is more than ten billion dollars a year, why shouldn't Georgia have a similar income if tourism develops, because out of 35 thousand historical monuments in the region, four are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Its itineraries also include visits to natural and cultural monuments, important historical sites (ski centers, hiking, mountaineering, botanical tours), medical resorts (cardiology, pulmonology, phthisiology, allergology, neurology, gastroenterology, arthrology, gynecology, nephrology, urology, dermatology), and itineraries on special topics in which interest has existed since antiquity.

At present, adventure tourism is mainly established in the Georgian market, which is a relatively new and just beginning to develop area. This type of tourism is popular, especially among young people. Its appearance on the market is associated with increased demand from the population and includes non-traditional tours, hiking, wildlife photography. The term "adventure

tourism" often includes ecotourism, but ecotourism, while often containing a certain element of adventure, does not always mean pure adventure. Adventure tourism is also often equated with sports tourism, although the purpose of sports tourism is to participate in sports or attend sports events. Adventure tourism, on the other hand, aims to gain new sensations and experiences through risky and extreme activities as well as spectacular performances.

At this stage, Georgia includes 105 of the best destinations for extreme tourism. In particular, there are interesting places both on the slopes of the North Caucasus and near the Black Sea, paragliding, jeep tours in the Gareja desert, Okatse canyon, as well as beautiful peaks and many attractions. It is also important that such a rest is quite accessible to any healthy person, even those who do not have special diseases.

In Georgia, the priority for the future is the development of agriculture and tourism, which should play an important role in the social development of the country in terms of:

- Consumption of local organic food by arriving tourists, which will replenish the state budget;
- Solving problems and stimulating sectors such as transport, communications, trade, construction, agriculture and consumer goods production.

Thus, as already mentioned, the flow of tourists is important for the development of the national economy, being a source of income. In this direction, the influx of foreign citizens to Georgia in 2025-2026 (see chart N1) according to the National Bureau of Statistics of Georgia is as follows.

Chart N1

Source: Geostat 2026

The charts presented show that by 2025, the total number of foreign tourists decreased by 0.3 compared to 2024, but after a certain period of time, when political, economic issues and tourist infrastructure in the country will be settled, one should expect a further increase in the number of foreign tourists and demand for

recreation, entertainment and treatment. Despite the decline in arrivals (see chart N2), according to the National Bureau of Statistics of Georgia, the country still received a record income of \$2 billion¹.

Chart N2

Source: Geostat 2025

The influx of tourists in business and professional activities is 39%, visiting friends and relatives - 26%, recreation and entertainment - 20%, transit - 4%, trade - 3%, medical care - 2%, education and training - 2%, work in an international organization - 2%, other goals

- 2%. As noted, the largest percentage is represented by the number of arrivals in business and professional activities. In terms of income from international travel (see chart N3), the highest income and percentage are observed in the following countries:

Chart N3

<https://api.gnta.ge/>

The largest influx of tourists (in thousands of US dollars) falls on: Russia (307,772), the European Union (277,049), Turkey (258,481), Israel (241,869), Azerbaijan (102,55), Saudi Arabia (38,781). In percentage terms, compared with previous years, the inflow from Russia decreased by 19%, from Turkey - by 10%, from Iran - by 12%. By mode of transport, most tourists arrived by road, followed by air, sea and rail.

According to the National Tourism Administration of Georgia², the number of tourists arriving in Georgia from other countries increased significantly in 2024. During the year, 5.79 million travelers visited the country, which is 4.1% more than

in 2023. However, in 2025 this figure will decrease by 0.3%. Despite the decrease in the number of visitors from Russia (1.11 million), Turkey (1.06 million) and Armenia (732,271), Georgia remains a popular tourist destination in these countries. Accordingly, it is necessary to study the existing potential and resources for the development of tourism in the country by region. A sector-specific database should also be established to support a long-term strategy for the tourism sector. In particular, it is cultural tourism; holidays at resorts; ecotourism; adventure tourism; agritourism; medical tourism (balneological resorts with mineral waters, sulfur baths, healing mud in

¹ National Bureau of Statistics of Georgia 2025

² Georgian National Tourism Administration 2025

Akhtala, etc.); business and professional tourism; sports tourism (mountaineering, etc.).

In Georgia in 2025, according to official data from the National Bureau of Statistics of Georgia, in addition to the number of tourists arriving from abroad, the number of visits from the local population has also decreased³. In particular, the average number of local visitors aged 15 and over was 1 million 333 thousand GEL, while last year this figure was 1 million 642 thousand GEL. Accordingly, the number of visitors during the specified period decreased by 1.6%, and the number of their visits was 0.2% higher than in 2024. As for the average number of tourist visits, it amounted to 700 thousand, which is 4.9% less than in 2024. The majority of visitors, 36.4%, are in the 31-50 age bracket and the proportion of women is 56.5% of total visitors. According to the results of the study, 36.8% of visitors are residents of Tbilisi, 15.6% come from Imereti, Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo-Svaneti regions, 9.3% - from the Autonomous Republic of Ajara, and the rest of the regions are represented by relatively small shares. Also, the average amount of expenses incurred during travel last year amounted to 297.7 million lari, which is 0.8% less than the same indicator in 2024.

Based on the above, the criteria for the development of tourism in Georgia can be determined by the following priorities:

- Export nature of tourism;
- High income growth potential of the country and the possibility of large-scale employment of the population;
- Availability of reserves to equalize the level of regional economic development.

These priorities will bring additional foreign exchange earnings to the population. However, this region must be managed with a sound strategic approach and development that creates a highly efficient, sustainable and environmentally responsible model that has a positive impact on both the environment and the economy and society. In addition to priorities, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

- The management process should take into account the traditions, socio-economic and cultural rights of the local population;
- To improve the socio-economic situation of the local population, catering establishments and family hotels should be organized. It is necessary to hire guides and develop ecotourism;
- Involving the population living in the region in tourism activities;
- Integration of environmental policy should be taken into account in the process of defining and creating categories of protected areas;
- To reduce risks, the link between the special tourism management system and the health sector needs to be strengthened.

Despite its drawbacks, Georgia remains an attractive tourist destination for foreign travelers and is showing steady growth, which is likely to continue in the coming years.

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